

Informed Consent Form for the PROTEST-AIRT project

Marie Skłodowska-Curie Postdoctoral Fellowship (Grant Agreement 101057156)

Title of Project - PROTEST-AIRT – Protesting the global air transport industry: Social movements fighting for the preservation of local communities and the planet.

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1. Purpose of the Study: The purpose of this research is to understand the contemporary global dissent against the air transport industry. The project investigates airport conflicts in Europe, with an emphasis in four cases: Berlin Brandenburg Airport in Germany, El Prat-Barcelona Airport in Spain, Bristol Airport in the United Kingdom, and Amsterdam Airport Schiphol in the Netherlands.

2. Procedures to be followed: As a result of your conversation with the researcher Dr Alexander Araya López, some written notes – including verbatim statements – will be taken. These written notes will be stored as a digital file in an external hard drive while being processed, and this external hard drive will be encrypted and kept at a secure location at the University of Potsdam. This digital file will not include your name or any personal information. The physical notes in paper will be destroyed after the pseudonymized digital file has been created. Contact information will be kept only in the consent form for notetaking, and it will only be used if the researcher decides to formally include you in a later phase of the project (for example, in an in-depth interview). Your name will be linked to pseudonymized digital file through a code. Any code linking your name to your pseudonymized digital file will be destroyed at the end of the project (June 30th, 2024). At that point your data will be completely anonymized.

3. Discomforts and Risks: There are some risks in participating in this research. Some of the questions are personal and might cause discomfort. You will be asked some questions about your activism, your organization, your opinions on political dissent against air transport in Europe and the potential solutions for air transport in the context of the climate crisis. Although the researcher will take all the possible measures to protect you as a participant, it cannot be completely ruled out that re-identification will be possible in the future through a combination with other data sources.

4. Benefits: The benefits to you include the opportunity share your thoughts about the climate emergency, about your experiences working in the sector, government or in media, and any political opinion regarding the global air transport industry both in Europe and abroad. The benefits to society include the development of a series of recommendations for policymakers, aiming both at informing

entrepreneurs and the air transport representatives about the needs of the local populations and at impacting the opinion-formation and decision-taking processes at the political level (for example, in the case of local governments). This research will contribute to understand the role that air transport plays in the current global climate crisis.

5. **Duration/Time:** The conversation with the researcher will only take a couple of minutes.
6. **Statement of Confidentiality:** Your participation in this research is voluntary and your identity and personal information will be protected. Some personal information that could identify who the responses belong to will be asked for contextual purposes (for example, age or gender) but this information will be kept in a secure location separated from the written notes of our conversation. No personally identifiable information will be shared in any publication or presentation resulting from this research, because your name and private data are not linked to the written notes.
7. **Right to Ask Questions:** Please contact the researcher Dr Alexander Araya López or the advisor Dr Jürgen Mackert with your questions, complaints, or concerns about this research. You can also contact them if you feel this study has harmed you. Questions about your rights as a research participant may be directed to the Ethics Committee at the University of Potsdam. For any data concerns, you can contact the Data Protection Officer, [\[ADD FULL NAME\]](#): [\[ADD EMAIL\]](#)
8. **Payment for participation:** Your participation is voluntary, and you will not be compensated in any form (economic or material) because of your contribution to this research.
9. **Voluntary Participation:** Your decision to be in this research is voluntary. You can stop at any time. You can refuse to answer any questions that make you feel uncomfortable or threatened. There will be no consequences for you if you decide to withdraw from this research (partially or completely). If you decide to withdraw from this study at a later phase, a statement of non-participation will be signed by the researcher, and all audio and textual data will be immediately destroyed.